

Deliverable 4.8: Upgrading multidisciplinary clinical expertise update

Period: 01/04/2021 – 28/02/2023

Author(s):	Lead author: Manousos Konstadoulakis (NKUA) Co-authors: Agapi Kataki (NKUA), Alena Gabelova (BMC SAV), Tatiana Šipošova (BMC SAV), Božena Smolkova (BMC SAV), Yvonne Kohl (FhG), Julie Earl (SERMAS/IRYCIS), Maria Dusinska (NILU)
Workpackage:	WP4
Task:	T4.4
Version:	2.0
Date:	28.02.2023

Contents

Basic information.....	3
Executive summary	4
1 Description of work & main achievements	4
1.1 Courses.....	4
1.1.1 Overview and Future Perspectives in Colorectal Cancer.....	4
1.1.2 The Treatment Landscape for Hepatocellular Carcinoma.....	5
1.1.3 Diagnostic and Therapeutic Aspects of Handling GPNETs	8
1.1.4 Online course on Gastrointestinal Stromal Tumours (GIST)	9
1.1.5 Statistical Analysis of Biomedical Data: Basic Principles and Practicals.....	10
1.2 Academic stays	12
1.3 Invited lectures	12
1.4 Regular meetings with clinicians.....	16
1.4.1 BMC SAV	16
1.4.2 NKUA.....	19
1.4.3 Educational video – Laparoscopic left pancreateomy: surgical steps	19
2 Deviation from the workplan	19
3 Conclusion	19

This report arises from the VISION project. The content of this report represents the views of the author/s only and is his/her/their sole responsibility; it cannot be considered to reflect the views of the European Commission and/or the Research Executive Agency or any other body of the European Union. The European Commission and the Agency do not accept any responsibility for use that may be made of the information it contains. The authors are not responsible for any further and future use of the report by third parties and third-party translations

Basic information

Project title	Strategies to strengthen scientific excellence and innovation capacity for early diagnosis of gastrointestinal cancers
Project acronym	VISION
Call	H2020-WIDESPREAD-2018-2020
Topic	WIDESPREAD-03-2018
Project type	Coordination and Supporting Action (CSA)
Grant Agreement No.	857381
Nature	R (Document, report - excluding the periodic and final reports);
Dissemination level	PU (Public, fully open, e.g. web);

Executive summary

Deliverable D4.8 describes the activities dedicated to mining and bridging the gaps between research and clinics. Cancer patients' treatment is becoming increasingly complex; therefore, the concept of a multidisciplinary team working for patients' benefit is considered the gold standard for improving patient outcomes. To do so, the cancer multidisciplinary team consists of surgeons, oncologists, radiologists, pathologists, specialist cancer nurses, physicians, experts in basic research, and psychologists. A successful multidisciplinary health team leads to a comprehensive assessment of a patient's situation and optimizes the treatment modalities to cure each patient. Therefore, one of the specific goals of the VISION project is to allow medical doctors and scientists to collaborate in such multidisciplinary teams within the hospital healthcare units.

1 Description of work & main achievements

Based on the positive responses to the digital form of education during the COVID-19 crisis, the VISION partners agreed to continue with the online form of courses and invited lectures. All educational activities implemented in the second period can be found on the VISION website:

https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1PZCR6QnBGzy3Olw3c_OOq1Vcu_hX9KXx?usp=sht

1.1 Courses

Several online courses were dedicated primarily to medical students. Their topics were related to training in treating patients with GI tumors and training in surgical operational procedures aiming to treat patients with GI, among other topics.

1.1.1 Overview and Future Perspectives in Colorectal Cancer

This course consisted of three lectures prepared by experts from the National and Kapodistrian University of Athens:

- ***Hereditary colorectal cancer syndromes*** - Dr. Agapi Katakis

Even though the majority of colorectal cancer cases diagnosed annually are due to sporadic events, up to 10% are attributed to hereditary factors. Known monogenic disorders include Lynch syndrome, Familial Adenomatous Polyposis, MUTYH-associated polyposis, Peutz Jeghers Syndrome, Cowden Syndrome and Juvenile polyposis Syndrome. Genetic counseling and testing of these patients are important issues leading to a substantial reduction in morbidity and mortality among themselves as well as their at risk families as inherited colorectal cancer syndromes confer a markedly increased risk for the development of multiple cancers

- ***Histological and molecular subtypes of colorectal cancer (CRC)*** - Dr. Efthymios Koniaris

The presentation was focused on the main histological subtypes of colorectal cancer as defined by WHO (2019): a) adenocarcinomas (NOS, adenoma-like, micropapillary, mucinous poorly cohesive, signet ring cell, medullary, adenosquamous and sarcomatoid), b) neuroendocrine tumors (G1-3, L-cell, glucagon-like, PP, serotonin and enterochromaffin cell), c) neuroendocrine carcinoma, d) mesenchymal tumors (GIST, kaposi sarcoma, leiomyosarcoma) and e) lymphomas (mantle cell, MALT, DLBCL).

Also, the four main molecular groups as classified by the Consensus Molecular Subtypes (CMS 2020) were analyzed. More specifically: 1. CMS1 (immune 15%, MSI, CpG island methylator phenotype (CIMP), BRAF mutation, hypermutated- immune activated, mainly in the right side of the colon), 2. CMS2 (Canonical 40%, MSS, Chromosomal Instability (CIN), Wnt/MYC activation, EGFR dependence- immune desert, mainly in the left side of the colon), 3. CMS3 (Metabolic 13%, CIN-MSI mixed, metabolic dysregulation, KRAS mutations- immune mixed, mainly in the right side of the colon), 4. CMS4 (mesenchymal 25%, MSS, CIN, stromal infiltration, TGF- β , angiogenesis- immune suppressed, both sides are affected).

- ***Surgery for Colon Cancer*** – Prof. Dervenis Christos

Cancer that begins in the colon (bowel or large intestine) or rectum is known as colorectal cancer

- The colon is about 5 feet long.
- Colorectal cancer can occur in any section of the colon or the rectum.

It is not known exactly what causes colorectal cancer

- But there are risk factors that increase chances for colorectal cancer:
 - Some risk factors cannot be changed---age, personal and family history
 - Some risk factors can be changed or eliminated---tobacco use, obesity, inactivity

Early stages of colorectal cancer may have NO signs or symptoms.

If signs and symptoms are present, they may include:

- Bleeding from the rectum or blood in the stool
- Marked change in bowel habits
- Abdominal mass
- Abdominal cramps or pain
- Iron deficiency anemia that is not due to other conditions

Tests used to look for colorectal cancer:

- Colonoscopy
- Flexible Sigmoidoscopy
- Fecal Occult Blood Test (FOBT)
- Double contrast barium enema

Treatment is based on an oncological surgical resection (based on the location) followed by chemotherapy (depending on the stage).

1.1.2 The Treatment Landscape for Hepatocellular Carcinoma

This course consisted of four lectures prepared by experts from the National and Kapodistrian University of Athens:

- ***Histological and molecular subtypes of hepatocellular carcinoma*** – Prof. Dina Tiniakos

Recent classification of hepatocellular carcinoma (HCC) is based on morphology and underlying molecular alterations recognising two main HCC subgroups, the proliferative with

worse prognosis (expression of stem cell markers, TP53 mutations, FGF19 amplification) and the non-proliferative (activation of JAK/STAT pathway, CTNNB1 activating mutations). New subtypes have been introduced in addition to classical HCC: massive macrotrabecular HCC (5-10% of HCC, high serum AFP, large size, trabeculae >6-cell thick in >50% of the tumour, predictor of HCC recurrence, TP53 mutations and FGF19 amplification); steatohepatic (steatosis, ballooning or Mallory–Denk bodies, fibrosis and inflammatory foci, JAK/STAT pathway activation, more common in patients with the metabolic syndrome and steatohepatitis in the background liver); and chromophobe HCC (5% of HCC, related to HBV infection, alternative lengthening of telomere (ALT) phenotype by telomere FISH). A specific fusion transcript, DNAJB1–PRKACA, has been identified in fibrolamellar carcinoma (FLC) subtype of HCC.

- **Locoregional therapies and patient profiling** – Prof. Ioannis Elefsiniotis

Hepatocellular carcinoma (HCC) represents approximately 80% of primary liver cancers and constitutes a major health problem worldwide. The vast majority of HCC cases occur in the setting of chronic liver disease, with cirrhosis being the primary risk factor for HCC, independent of liver disease aetiology. Locoregional therapies includes the ablative techniques (mostly radiofrequency and microwave ablation) as well as intraarterial therapies (transarterial chemoembolization and radioembolization with yttrium-90 microspheres) and are currently recommended for patients with HCC in very early (BCLC 0) or early (BCLC A) stages, as a curative approach, and in intermediate stages (BCLC B) as a palliative treatment, as well as a bridging therapy in patients listed for liver transplantation or for down staging the disease in carefully selected patients of early BCLC-B stage in order to become candidates for surgical treatment (either resection or liver transplantation).

Ablative techniques using chemical or thermal energy have been developed and established in the loco-regional therapy of HCCs over the last three decades. They recommended in very early stage (single lesion < 2 cm) and early stage (single or 2-3 nodules < 3 cm each) cancers amongst patients who are not candidates for surgical resection or transplantation. Transcatheter arterial chemoembolization (TACE) represents the therapeutic gold-standard (evidence IA) in a subgroup of patients' unsuitable for surgery and for percutaneous ablation techniques, with multinodular HCC and preserved liver function (intermediate stage, BCLC-B), without vascular invasion or extra-hepatic spread that both characterize the advanced HCC stage (BCLC-C). Transarterial radioembolization (TARE) has been investigating in patients with HCC of various stages (for disease downstaging in BCLC-A patients awaiting liver transplantation, in comparison with TACE in BCLC-B or with sorafenib in BCLC-C patients), showing good safety profile and local disease control but failure to show overall survival benefit, so the subgroup of patients benefitting from TARE needs to be further evaluated.

Moreover there are preliminary data suggesting the immune modulating effects of locoregional therapy and its potential synergy with systemic treatment (mainly immunotherapy) in patients with advanced HCC stages, and we are eagerly awaiting the results from many randomized controlled trials in the near future.

- **Surgical Treatment in HCC** - Prof. Christos Dervenis

Primary cancer of the liver that originates from the hepatocytes

Incidence is rising specially in the Western countries mostly because of new risk factors and also because of higher sensitivity of the detections methods

Risk factors for HCC are:

- Alcohol liver damage
- Hepatitis
- Toxins
- Metabolic (Diabetes, Dyslipidemia, Metabolic Syndrome)
- Smoking
- Non-alcoholic fatty liver disease and non-alcoholic steatohepatitis which are rising in the Western hemisphere with alarming rates but also in the developing areas of the eastern countries
- Fibrosis/Cirrhosis of the liver from any kind of other causes

Diagnosis is based on medical imaging and biopsy rather than symptoms which often come when the cancer has progressed in late stages

Many cases of HCC though arise without any evident liver pathology and are called sporadic.

Cirrhotic patients or known to have a liver threatening disease are at a regular follow up and have a chance of being diagnosed at an earlier stage of cancer.

Treatment depends on the timing of diagnosis which translates in a combination of the cancer stage and the level of liver function or cirrhosis:

- Early stages benefit from surgical resection
- Later Stages benefit from local other than surgical and systemic treatment
- **Systemic Treatments and Immunotherapy in HCC** – Prof. Ioannis Koskinas

Systemic therapies are recommended for patients in advanced disease stages (BCLC stage C) or for patients in intermediate-stage disease stages (BCLC stage B) that are not (or no longer) eligible for locoregional therapies.

Until recently, sorafenib and lenvatinib (TKIs) were the first line treatment for HCC followed by regorafenib or cabozantinib as a second line in patients who developed progression or intolerance to first line drugs. TKIs' side effects include fatigue, diarrhea, hypertension and hand-foot syndrome.

Currently immunotherapy has been introduced in the treatment of HCC based on the utility of immune checkpoint inhibitors. The first combination that has been approved (atezolizumab plus bevacizumab) when compared to sorafenib as first line treatment showed better results with up to 35% objective response rate and therefore has replaced TKIs as first line treatment.

Many studies with immunotherapy drugs in combination are underway with promising efficacy. However immune markers for identification of immunologically "hot" HCC and evaluation of treatment response in clinical practice are still lacking.

1.1.3 Diagnostic and Therapeutic Aspects of Handling GPNETs

This course consisted of three lectures prepared by experts from the National and Kapodistrian University of Athens:

- **Introduction to GPNETs** – Prof. Georgios Mastorakos

Gastroenteropancreatic neuroendocrine neoplasms (GPNENs) are rare neoplasms arising from the neuroendocrine cells that secrete bioactive substances, in the blood stream causing distinct clinical syndromes. This group of NENs is denoted as functioning NENs; however, the majority of NENs are non-functioning. According to the most recent 2019 WHO classification, the diagnosis of a NEN is based on both its differentiation and proliferative activity, ranging from the well-differentiated neuroendocrine tumours (NETs) of grade G1, G2, or G3, to the poorly differentiated neuroendocrine carcinomas (NECs) G3. The grade in various tumour entities has been categorised based on their Ki-67 level of expression. Their prognosis depends mainly on grading and staging systems but also on the tissue of origin of the primary tumor. Well-differentiated NETs have a prolonged survival in the absence of metastatic disease; however, a subset may display a truly aggressive behavior exhibiting a poor prognosis.

- **Surgery as a Treatment for GP-NETs** – Prof. Christos Dervenis

GEP – Net's are classified in relation to:

- Primary Site
- Functional or Non-Functional
- Grade
- TNM Stage
- Carcinoid Syndrome = in 30% of cases

The role of surgery has as follows:

- Intention to Treat – Prolong OS
- Improve QoL – alleviate symptoms from Functional NETs and also sometimes improve OS
- Prevent or Treat Local Complications

Different types of surgery could be offered:

- Radical Oncologic Resection
- Conservative Resection – Enucleations – Organ Preserving
- Palliative Resection
- Resection for Local Complications like Bleeding, Obstruction, Pain, Ischaemia (often in Small Bowel NETs)

Metastatic GEP – NETs

- ✓ Liver is almost the only site for a surgical approach in the metastatic disease from GEP NETs.
- ✓ The indications should be taken following a stepwise algorithm which would take into account both the aggressiveness of the disease and the pattern of diffusion into the liver.
- ✓ Since the low level of scientific evidence any decision should be taken only after MDTs discussion.

- **Therapeutic Spectrum in GPNETs** – Dr. Krystallenia Alexandraki

Neuroendocrine neoplasms (NENs) are rare neoplasms and arise mainly in the gastrointestinal or pulmonary system. Most gastroenteropancreatic NENs (GPNENs) are well-differentiated neuroendocrine tumours (GPNETs) with prolonged survival in the absence of metastatic disease; however, a subset may display a truly aggressive behaviour exhibiting a poor prognosis. The grade of differentiation defining tumour classification along with advances in immunohistochemistry and functional imaging help to the choice of the treatment. Surgery is the mainstay of treatment of NENs for localized disease with intention to treat or for cytoreduction. In case of locally or regionally advanced or metastatic disease medical treatment is followed. Long-acting somatostatin analogues are the first line treatment for functioning GPNETs in order to control the secretive syndrome but also for non-functioning GPNETs in order to achieve tumour growth stabilization. Other systemic treatments include interferon- α for functioning small bowel NETs, molecular and peptide receptor radionuclide targeted treatments for less aggressive neoplasms, while chemotherapy, and recently immunotherapy, are both reserved for more aggressive neoplasms. New agents such as telotristat are used to control carcinoid syndrome. The appropriate sequence of therapeutic agents is still to be defined, and the choice of monotherapy or combination therapy should be individualized in the context of the site of origin, TNM staging and grading, extension of liver disease, presence of clinical syndrome, patients' performance status, availability of therapeutic techniques and patient choice. Advances in the molecular pathogenesis of NENs and larger prospective studies will shed light on biomolecular tumour markers that may suggest the appropriate sequence of treatment in each individual patient.

1.1.4 Online course on Gastrointestinal Stromal Tumours (GIST)

This course consisted of three lectures prepared by experts from the National and Kapodistrian University of Athens:

- **Surgical challenges of GIST tumors** – Nikolaos Memos, MD, Ph.D.

Gastrointestinal Stroma Tumours are rare mesenchymal neoplasms that are mainly located at the gastrointestinal tract. Most commonly involve the stomach, with second most common location the small bowel but they are also seen at the esophagus, rectum, duodenum etc. The treatment cornerstone of GIST is surgical removal with negative margins (R0 resection). GISTs are diagnosed as soft tissue tumour either as incidental finding in imaging scans or as the cause of GI symptoms such as early satiety, bloating, ileus or GI bleeding. Prognosis of GIST depends on the size of the tumour that ranges from couple of cm to >10 cms, the mitotic index and the GI location. In addition, the risk of tumour rupture either spontaneously or iatrogenically is independent malprognostic factor. The surgical challenges for the GISTs mainly involve the location of the tumour and the extend of the resection. Large tumours located at the stomach, the duodenum or at the rectum may require multivisceral resection increasing mortality and morbidity. In the imatinib era, the neoadjuvant treatment and the advances in the surgical techniques, the R0 resections can now be more applicable. However, the response seen following treatment is mainly partial, making the multivisceral resection still the main treatment modality for curing the patient. In the present lecture we will discuss the challenges that a surgical oncologist faces when asked to operate at the GIST tumours in the post imatinib area. In addition, we will discuss the input of minimally invasive surgical techniques for the treatment of GIST.

- **Targeted therapy for GIST** – Jose Duran Moreno, MD, MSc.

Gastrointestinal Stroma Tumours are rare mesenchymal neoplasms that are mainly located at the gastrointestinal tract. Carcinogenesis of GISTs is driven in about 85% of cases by a punctual mutation of gene c-kit or pdgfra. This knowledge permitted the successful development of several therapies that, targeting these mutations, improve the survival and quality of life of patients with unresectable GIST, turning this tumor into the pioneer and paradigm of targeted therapy in solid tumors. In the present lecture we will discuss the achievements, limitations and challenges of target therapy in GIST.

- **Gastrointestinal stromal tumours: Histology and genetics** – George Agrogiannis, MD, MSc.

GISTs are the most common clinically significant mesenchymal neoplasm of the GI tract. Population-based studies estimate the annual incidence at 10 cases per million. They are found along the entire length of the digestive tract but are most common in the stomach. No etiologic factors related to GIST have been identified and although the vast majority of GISTs occur as sporadic tumors with somatic mutations, GISTs also occur rarely in various tumor syndromes. The lesions vary in their cellularity, ranging from low, to intermediate, to high. Regarding the immunoreactivity in gastrointestinal stromal tumors, a cytoplasmic pattern for KIT B, a dot-like or membranous pattern are all common. For DOG1 expression, the membranous staining pattern is typical. Understanding underlying mutations in GISTs is critical for diagnosis and patient care, and these are tumors with quite well-defined molecular alterations which reflects to the targeted therapy. Imatinib is the mostly used drug agent for the therapy of GISTs. Four different regions of KIT, namely exon 9, exon 11, exon 13, and exon 17, are most often mutated in sporadic GISTs. Exon 18, exon 12, and exon 14 are the 3 PDGFRA regions that are mutated in GISTs. Fifteen (15) percent of the tumors do not harbor either the KIT or PDGFRA mutations and they are designated as Wild Type GISTs, while a small subset harbors SDH mutations. A subset of GISTs lack mutations in the KIT/PDGFR A or RAS pathways and yet retain an intact SDH complex. It was proposed that these tumors could be designated as quadruple wild-type (WT) GIST. GISTs demonstrate diverse clinical profiles in that they can arise in any part of the GI tract and can present as tumors ranging from incidental microscopic tumors to those that follow a malignant and life-threatening course by metastasis. This diversity is also reflected in the oncogenic events that lead to their development.

1.1.5 Statistical Analysis of Biomedical Data: Basic Principles and Practicals

The course aims to provide participants with a basic understanding of terms and methods of statistical data analysis, with a specific focus on practical exercise and familiarization with statistical applications in biomedical research.

COURSE OUTLINE

Course title	Statistical Analysis of Biomedical Data: Basic Principles and Practicals
Lecturer	Marilena Anastasaki, MSc (Biostatistics), PhD candidate
Course type	Online lectures (theory and practice using the SPSS statistical package)

Duration	30 hours (divided into 10 three-hour lectures)
Course dates	4 – 15 October 2021 (lectures) and 18 – 29 October 2021 (AOB including supplementary courses, individual communications, or revision courses based on the audience needs)
Course time	15.00 – 18.00 CET
Course language	English
Learning objectives	The course aims to provide participants with a basic understanding of terms and methods of statistical data analysis, with a specific focus on practical exercise and familiarization with statistical applications in biomedical research.
General skills	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Adjustment 2. Decision making 3. Individual work 4. Teamwork 5. Critical thinking 6. Promotion of free, creative, and inductive thinking 7. Data/evidence review, analysis, and synthesis using technology
Course outline	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Descriptive Statistics <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Variables and data types b. Central tendency and variance indicators c. Distributions and graphs d. Introduction to SPSS: variable entry and coding, data entry and management 2. Inferential Statistics <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Population and sample b. Confidence intervals and hypothesis testing c. Univariate analysis (χ^2 test, Student's t-test, Mann-Whitney test, one-way ANOVA, Kruskal-Wallis test, Pearson and Spearman correlation coefficients, Paired t-test, Wilcoxon sign rank test, ANOVA for repeated measurements) d. Linear regression (simple and multiple linear regression, model interpretation) e. Logistic regression (hypothesis testing and model fitting, interpretation of model coefficients) f. Survival analysis g. SPSS practicals

References	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. James F Jekel, Joann G. Elmore, David L. Katz. Epidemiology, Biostatistics, and Preventive Medicine. Yale University, New Haven, CT, 1996 2. Nigel Bruce, Daniel Pope, Debbi Stanistreet. Quantitative Methods for Health Research. A Practical Interactive Guide to Epidemiology and Statistics. Wiley, 2018
Requirements	<p>Download the free 30-day SPSS trial version: https://www.ibm.com/analytics/spss-trials</p>

1.2 Academic stays

- **Dr Peter Dubovan**, a medical doctor doing his specialization in Surgery, joined the team of Prof M. Konstadoulakis in the 2nd Department of Surgery in Aretaieio Hospital for a month in summer 2022 (21/8/2021-19/9/2021) after his initial visit was postponed due to covid-19 travelling restrictions. The courses attended were Training in surgical operational procedures aiming to treat patients with GI, Training in enrolling patients with GI tumours in research protocols and Training in surgical operational procedures aiming to treat patients with GI.
- **Ioanna Aggelioudaki**, a PhD student in the 2nd Department of Surgery, Aretaieio Hospital joined the group of 'Ramón y Cajal Health Research Institute' attending the following courses: "*The use of the liquid biopsy in precision medicine*" and "*The use of mouse models in oncology research*", from January 10 to February 2, 2022
- **Emma Barreto Melián**, a Ph.D. student from 'Ramón y Cajal Health Research Institute' joined the team in the 2nd Department of Surgery in Aretaieio Hospital for one month from January 18 to February 17, 2023. The courses attended were: "*Initiation in Medical Genetics and Genetic Counselling*", "*Training in exosome isolation methodology*", "*Training in Circulating tumour cells isolation methodology*", and "*Training in protein expression analysis*".

1.3 Invited lectures

In the second period of VISION project implementation, eight invited lectures were performed:

- **Microfluidic technologies and their applications in cell biology** – Thorsten Knoll, MSc., Eng. of Microsystems Technology, Cell Models & Toxicology, senior scientist, Fraunhofer Institute of Biomedical Engineering IBMT, Sulzbach, Germany, on April 27, 2021 (Number of participants: 31)

- **Bariatric surgery and non-alcoholic fatty liver disease** – Pantelis Antonakis MD, Ph.D., the 2nd Department of Surgery Athens Medical School, "Aretaieion Hospital", Athens Greece, on June 16, 2021 (Number of participants: 29)

- **Genomic instability, microenvironment and telomere homeostasis in colorectal cancer** – Pavel Vodička, MD, Ph.D., Head of the Department of Molecular Tumor Biology, Institute of Experimental Medicine CAS, Prague, Czech Republic, on November 11, 2021 (Number of participants: 40)

- **Objective: Personalised Prevention of Pancreatic Cancer** – Núria Malats, MD, Ph.D., Head of the Genetic and Molecular Epidemiology Group, Spanish National

Cancer Research Centre (CNIO), Madrid, Spain, on December 16, 2021 (Number of participants: 19)

- **New Perspectives in Clinical Trials** – Prof. Stefano Bonassi, Ph.D., ERT, Department of Human Sciences and Quality of Life Promotion, San Raffaele University, Head of the Unit of Clinical and Molecular Epidemiology, IRCCS San Raffaele Roma, Italy, on June 15, 2022 (Number of participants: 33)

- **Re-education of TAMs with lipid nanoparticles reduce liver metastasis in PDAC** – Bruno Sainz, Jr., Ph.D., Head of the Cancer Stem Cells and Fibroinflammatory Microenvironment Group, Instituto de Investigaciones Biomédicas "Alberto Sols" CSIC-UAM, Instituto Ramón y Cajal de Investigación Sanitaria (IRYCIS), Madrid, Spain, on October 5, 2022 (Number of participants: 42)

- **Next-Generation Sequencing in Cancer Research and Diagnosis** – Pantelis Hatzis, Ph.D., Head of the Fleming Genomic and Precision Medicine Facility and the Genomics & Transcriptomic Unit of pMedGR at the Medical School of the University of Athens, Greece, on February 1, 2023 (Number of participants: 33)

- **Radiomics and radiogenomics in cancer** – Carolina De la Pinta, MD, Radiation Oncologist, Ramon y Cajal University Hospital (IRYCIS), Madrid, Spain, on February 8, 2023 (Number of participants: 30)

1.4 Regular meetings with clinicians

1.4.1 BMC SAV

BMC SAV participated in the following joint meetings (individual participating institutions abbreviated as NOU – National Cancer Institute, SAV – BMC SAV, UK – Comenius University in Bratislava):

Online meeting NOU-SAV-UK – May 6, 2021

Online meeting regarding the use of CRC samples and the possibility of submission of a joint project proposal within Horizon Europe call

Participants:

Prof. Michal Mego (NOU)

MUDr. Peter Dubovan (NOU)

MUDr. Miroslav Tomáš (NOU)

Employees of Science Park UK lead by Dr. Tomáš Szemes

Dr. Miroslava Matúšková (BMC SAV)

Dr. Martina Poturnajová (BMC SAV)

Meeting NOU-SAV – May 20, 2021

Participants:

Prof. Michal Mego (NOU)

Dr. Božena Smolková (BMC SAV)

Dr. Miroslava Matúšková (BMC SAV)

Dr. Martina Poturnajová (BMC SAV)

Topic – submission of a joint national project proposals focusing on PDAC and CRC

Pancreatic cancer (PDAC) as a research model has several advantages:

- The worst diagnosis
- Slovakia-specific
- Screening via biopsy is problematic, there is a need for new screening methods and stratification of patients
- Monitoring of patients from diagnosis to palliative care within the project timeframe
- Possibility to involve several clinicians from different units of patient care

Task: To find molecular biomarkers which will reflect differences in the overall survival of patients and differences in the disease relapse after the elimination of primary PDAC tumor.

CRC project: Circulation biomarkers highly sensitive and specific for personal monitoring of CRC patients during the whole disease (and possibly after treatment). Potential higher representation of genetic mutations.

Virtual meeting NOU-SAV – May 28, 2021

Conference call regarding current stratification of CRC patients.

Participants:

MUDr. Peter Dubovan (NOU)

Dr. Martina Poturnajová (BMC SAV)

Topics:

- Patients' data and sample collection.
- The possibility to identify patients treated by chemotherapy who developed resistance.
- The possibility to surgically obtain pre-tumor stage tissues from patients - adenoma or NO - mucosa of the large intestine during colonoscopy.
- Individual steps necessary for obtaining the ethics committee's approval for GIT malignancies and informed consent of the CRC patient?

Meeting NOU-SAV – November 6, 2021

Participants:

Dr. Miroslava Matúšková (BMC SAV)

Dr. Martina Poturnajová (BMC SAV)

MUDr. Peter Dubovan (NOU)

Topics:

- Inclusive/exclusive criteria for selecting patients for the study (a joint national APVV project proposal).
- Using "Clinical risk score".
- Estimation of number of patients/year.
- Patient stratification – early against late recurrence.

Meeting NOU-SAV – November 13, 2021

Participants:

Dr. Miroslava Matúšková (BMC SAV)

Dr. Martina Poturnajová (BMC SAV)

Prof. Michal Mego (NOÚ)

Dr. Božena Smolková (BMC SAV)

Topic: Finalization of details for joint proposals submitted to the general national call of the APVV agency.

Submitted proposals:

Identification of novel biomarkers linked to the relapse of metastatic colorectal cancer after metastasectomy – Science Park UK, BMC SAV, NOÚ

Reprogramming pancreatic ductal adenocarcinoma microenvironment towards immunotherapy – BMC SAV, NOÚ, UK

Meeting NOU-SAV – October 29, 2022

Participants:

Prof. Michal Mego (NOÚ)

Dr. Božena Smolková (BMC SAV)

Topic: The possibility of the collaborating organizations to join the COST action CA21116 - Identification of biological markers for prevention and translational medicine in pancreatic cancer (TRANSPAN), PANDoRA - The PANcreatic Disease ReseArch Consortium <https://pandoraconsortium.wixsite.com/pandora> and PRECEDE Consortium - The Pancreatic Cancer Early Detection <https://precedestudy.org/>.

Meeting NOU-SAV – January 30, 2023

Participants:

Dr. Božena Smolková (BMC SAV)

Dr. Marína Cihová (BMC SAV)

Dr. Verona Buociková (BMC SAV)

MUDr. Ján Slopovský (NOU)

Topic:

- Brainstorming on the implementation of experiments for a project aimed at sensitizing PDAC tumors to immunotherapy
- Workflow of samples, harmonization between the clinic and experimental workspace between tissue and peripheral blood collection
- Critical issues for the development of patient-derived models (PDX, organoids)

Meeting NOU-SAV – February 13, 2023

Participants:

Dr. Božena Smolková (BMC SAV)

Dr. Marína Cihová (BMC SAV)

Dr. Verona Buociková (BMC SAV)

MUDr. Ján Slopovský (NOU)

Gergo Borka, MSc.

Topic:

- Critical issues for the separation of individual lymphocyte populations were discussed, focusing on the possibilities of their co-cultivation with tumor and stromal cells
- Several co-cultivation models were presented by Ms. Borka and discussed
- Methods for molecular characterization of the individual cell population were compared

1.4.2 NKUA

Final year students of the Athens Medical School doing their training in General Surgery followed an educational programme on the role of Molecular Biology and Medical Genetics in the treatment of Oncological patients.

1.4.3 Educational video – Laparoscopic left pancreatectomy: surgical steps

Pantelis Antonakis MD, Ph.D., Laparoscopic and Robotic Surgeon at the Aretaieion Hospital, 2nd Department of Surgery, National and Kapodistrian University of Athens, Greece prepared an education video for medical students. The video is available on demand because it contains explicit content. Who is interested to see it has to contact the Project manager, Tatiana Siposova, MSc. (tatiana.siposova@savba.sk)

2 Deviation from the workplan

The theoretical expertise of those interested in the field is continuously enriched to enable them to prepare for the real clinical setting in the near future, so no deviation from the workplan exists.

3 Conclusion

The **training** activities within the VISION project allowed **exchange** and **translation** of **knowledge** among all partners in the consortium and upgraded the scientific and clinical potential toward understanding and performing **innovative biomedical translational research**.